

The Use of Computer Technology (Multimedia) in Physical Education Lessons by Students of Pedagogical Universities

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Abstract:

This article provides information on the introduction of computer technology, information technology, and multimedia into the learning process. Computer learning technology is considered as learning based on the final results of students' activities, and it is given the character of a sustainable, purposeful and effective learning process.

Keywords: multimedia technologies, multimedia training programs, sports and pedagogical disciplines.

Computer technologies as part of information technology form a fundamentally different style of work, which turns out to be more psychologically acceptable, comfortable, mobilizing creative possibilities and intellectual potential of a person.

The creation of new computer technology is not an end in itself, first of all it is aimed at using computer technology in scientific research, production, everyday life, sports, for the implementation of educational and other socially significant tasks. Providing the educational process with computer programs has always accompanied the development of theoretical and practical thought on their effective use in teaching activities. In this regard, the issues of the development of the theory and practice of using computer technologies in the educational process are of scientific interest.

The main requirement for automated learning systems should be their organic compliance with psychophysiological models of activity and learning

With regard to the practical use of computer programs in the educational process, this means:

Carefully worked out motivation for learning not only of a "forced" nature (assessment), but also personal interest and satisfaction with the educational process;

Evaluation of the final result, wide freedom of choice, encouragement of reasonable creativity in the learning process;

An individual approach to the student and his adaptation in the learning process.

Computer learning technology is considered as learning based on the final results of students' activities, and it is given the character of a sustainable, purposeful and effective learning process.

The use of computer technology in teaching is a kind of cognitive activity management process.

Learning management involves two interrelated processes: the organization of student activities and the control of these activities. These processes interact continuously: the result of the control affects the content of the control actions.

In turn, the organization of a certain activity requires both a certain form of control and a specific way of registering this activity. Combinations of these processes and transitions from one to the other are possible. This or a similar approach is recommended when creating programs not only for higher education, but also for secondary schools. Let's look at a number of examples.

The concept examines the components of the cognition process, exploring it in connection with the possibilities of enhancing the autonomy of learning. The concept of computerization of the learning process is based on a set of subjective desires, prerequisites and objective possibilities of organizing a rational learning process using intellectual components of computer technology.

The concept of using computer programs in the educational process includes:

- classification of a computer program;
- a schematic diagram of the permanent process of improving the educational process using an evolutionary computer;
- principles of using computer technologies in the educational process;
- Integrated use of information technologies.

The essence of the proposed learning concept is the systematic use of computer programs in combination with other information technologies necessary to create an individual human learning algorithm. The computer is directly integrated into the information technology of learning and becomes such a desirable element of the educational system that, in its absence, there is a certain discomfort for both the student and the teacher.

Computer learning technology, based on the information provided by the concept, considers learning taking into account the final results of students' activities, giving it the character of a sustainable, purposeful and effective learning process.

Educational computer programs are divided into electronic textbooks and electronic textbooks. Computer programs include, as a rule, various types of illustrative representation of the material: static type, planar animation and in the form of computer video animation, or complex multimedia (various combinations of audio, video, animation, etc.).

Controlling computer programs can be conditionally divided into three areas:

- management;
- knowledge control;
- monitoring of the state of individual body systems.

Information computer programs can be either embedded in training or control programs, or autonomous. Information computer programs can be divided as follows:

- reference and bibliographic;
- encyclopedic;
- narrowly thematic.

According to the access method, programs can be open or closed. For the owners, or rather developers, of these programs, they are usually open, and for users they can be both open and closed.

Information tools in physical education include computer, audio and video programs, and printed materials.

The optimal situation is when a teacher or student has the opportunity to choose any means of information technology on a specific topic of the program for use in the educational process.

Information thematic complexes may include methodological developments purposefully created for a specific task, or methodological developments for complex purposes.

The Flexibility Complex

The information thematic complex "Flexibility" includes information materials that help to study theoretical aspects and practical development of technology for the development of flexibility. The complex is intended for use in educational and extracurricular processes, during independent studies of students. It includes:

1. Printed textbook "Technology of flexibility development".
2. Educational video "Technology of flexibility development".

The developments included in the complex complement each other well, revealing each its own separate aspect. Thus, the printed textbook "Technology of flexibility development" allows you to study theoretical materials on terminology, structure and features of joint functioning, monitoring and self-monitoring of the level of flexibility development, regulation of physical activity. It also presents an illustrated set of exercises for developing flexibility. A direct continuation of this manual is the educational video "Technology for the development of flexibility". The film shows and tells about the sequence of selection of exercises for the development of flexibility, special attention is paid to exercises that are quite difficult in terms of methodology, depending on the type of exercise, the number of performers (from one to four) is selected.

The complex "Aerobics, shaping"

When implementing the principles of humanization and humanitarization in the pedagogical process of physical education of students, we drew attention to the natural interest of girls in everything related to their figure, physique, posture, and this section of the discipline "physical culture" is one of the most important for many. Based on this interest, or rather on its provision, we have prepared a thematic complex "Aerobics, shaping", which includes four developments:

1. Printed textbook "Learn to model your figure".
2. The computer program "Mini-shaping".
3. The computer program "Grace".
4. The computer program "Grace - competition".

The printed textbook "Learn to model your figure" contains the basis of theoretical knowledge necessary for organizing shaping classes with students within the framework of educational, extracurricular and independent studies. The manual includes sections on computer modeling, nutrition, control, and exercise complexes.

A computer program "Mini-shaping" has been developed specifically for use in the educational process, which allows solving four main tasks. The first is an educational beginning, which encourages students to further independently familiarize themselves with various methodological materials on this issue. The second is the determination of an individual range of standards for measurements (weight, circumference, diameters, body composition, physical fitness, etc.). The third is the acquisition of knowledge and skills to carry out measurement procedures and correlate the data obtained with model values. The fourth is to determine for each student the real tasks of figure correction and physical fitness for the next 3-4 months.

References

1. Bogdanov V.M., Ponomarev V.S., Solovov A.V. The use of modern information technologies in theoretical and methodological-practical training of students in physical education / Mater. All-Russian Scientific and Practical Conference St. Petersburg, 2000.
2. Volkov V.Yu. Computer technologies in the educational process of physical culture / Mater. All-Russian Scientific and Practical Conference St. Petersburg, 2000.
3. Zaitseva T.I., Smirnova O.Yu. In the collection: Information technologies in education. Moscow, 2000.
4. Lisitskaya, T.S. The use of a multimedia computer program in the process of training specialists in aerobics / T.S. Lisitskaya, I.M. Belyaeva // Theory and practice of physical culture and sports. - 2007. - No. 4. - pp. 25-28.
5. Miroshina, E.N. The use of information technologies in physical education / E.N. Miroshina // XXII International Scientific Congress "Modern Olympic and Paralympic sports for all". - 2008. - Volume 3. - pp. 202-203.